

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Report on surface radiation balance in SR-ESMs compared against observational products and coarse resolution simulation
Deliverable number	D48 (Del. Rel. No. D9.3)
Planned delivery date	31/07/2025
Actual date of issue	18/07/2025
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	WU
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

The report summarizes the evaluation of the representation of the components of the surface radiation balance from the SR-ESMs.

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WP9

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Executive summary

With the emergence of storm-resolving global climate models, approaching horizontal grid spacings of only a few kilometers, we expect a better representation of the surface irradiance climatology via three possible pathways i) synoptic variability may be better represented, ii) convective systems may be better resolved, and iii) landscape heterogeneity is represented in more detail. This report presents the results of work package 9.3, where we evaluate the performance of the nextGEMS simulations in produce accurate mean downwelling surface irradiances and investigate which pathways dominate the impact of horizontal resolution on surface irradiances. For the evaluation, we use all 5-year cycle 3 (IFS: 4.4 km, 9 km, and 28 km; ICON: 5 km) and 30-year cycle 4 (IFS: 9 km; ICON: 10 km) simulations. Most simulations have global annual mean biases within only 4.5 W m^{-2} and 7.6 W m^{-2} for solar and thermal irradiance, respectively, although local irradiance biases with respect to station measurements can be up to an order of magnitude higher. Furthermore, we find no clear and consistent improvement of mean surface irradiances as we move towards higher resolutions. We then focus on the cycle 3 IFS simulations, ranging from 4.4 km to 28 km horizontal resolution, to study in detail how differences in horizontal resolution affect the surface irradiance climatology. We find that differences in mean surface irradiance are most pronounced in areas with high orographic variability, suggesting that the better resolved orography is the main pathway of resolution-driven changes in the surface irradiance climatology. The representation of the cloud-driven local irradiance variability on hourly to daily time scales also improves with horizontal resolution, although these improvement do not carry over to larger spatiotemporal scales. Our findings suggest that for an accurate representation of the surface irradiance climatology, the added value of moving towards higher horizontal resolution among the nextGEMS simulations is still modest and may not yet outweigh the additional computational costs.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	yes
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP9	Relevance in this deliverable?
Investigate whether resolving the storm-scale variability in weather systems and in the land surface, together with their consistent interactions with the larger scales, affects the climatology of blocking, the statistics of dry and warm spells, the mean surface radiation balance as well as near-term changes in aggregated temperature and precipitation statistics (O2)	yes
Quantify the carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe at storm-resolving resolution and compare these estimates to ones from current ESMs (O2)	no
Use the production runs to reassess solar power on the global scale and to produce global maps of hazardous weather at unprecedented resolution (O3)	no

Synergies

The deliverable builds upon work package 8.1, specifically the initial validation of the surface energy budget in the Cycle 3 simulations in deliverable D8.1.

1 Detailed report on the deliverable

1.1 Introduction

With the emergence of km-scale grid spacings, we hope that global climate models produce increasingly more realistic surface irradiance climatologies on both global and local scales. Furthermore, we expect the representation of the temporal surface irradiance variability to improve, especially at hourly to daily time scales, as the horizontal resolution increases. These improvements with increasing horizontal resolution may occur via three pathways: Firstly, landscape features such as orography, coastlines, or land use heterogeneities are better resolved, likely resulting in a better representation of both terrain-induced local flow patterns and altitude-driven variability in near-surface temperature and cloud radiative forcing (Marty et al., 2002). Secondly, a better representation of cloud systems due to partially resolved deep convection likely results in more realistic diurnal cycles of cloud type and cloud cover (Prein et al., 2015). Thirdly, as small-scale improvements in the representation of orography and convection affect larger-scale circulation patterns (e.g. Sandu et al., 2019; Schiemann et al., 2020; Davini et al., 2022), we may also expect changes in surface irradiance due to shifts in dominant synoptic weather patterns or climate zones with horizontal resolution.

In this report, we present the results of deliverable 9.3, where we evaluate the surface solar and thermal irradiance climatologies, as well as their dependency on horizontal resolution, of the nextGEMS simulations. The results shown in this report are also part of an upcoming manuscript (preprint available; Veerman and Heerwaarden, 2025). We address the following two research questions:

1. How well do the simulations reproduce mean surface irradiances?
2. How does horizontal resolution impact surface irradiances?

To address the first question, we validate mean surface irradiances both on global and local scales. We mostly focus on downwelling surface irradiances over land, because of the tight coupling to surface processes and the relevance for photovoltaic energy production. To address the second research question, we assess the contribution of the three anticipated pathways of improvement, i) more detailed landscapes, ii) better resolved cloud systems, and iii) better resolved synoptic variability, on the surface irradiance climatology.

1.2 Data & Methods

For this deliverable, we use most of the ICON and IFS simulations from the third and fourth development cycles of the project. The simulations used in this report are summarized in Table 3. We provide a short description of the simulations in section 1.2.1 and of the reference data in 1.2.2.

Table 3: Overview of nextGEMS simulations used in this report. Δx_{atm} (km) is the resolution of the land and atmosphere and Δx_{oce} (km) is the resolution of the ocean.

Name	Δx_{atm} (km)	Δx_{oce} (km)	Period	Forcing
C3-IFS4.4	4.4	5	2020 - 2024	2020 (constant)
C3-IFS9	9	25	2020 - 2024	2020 (constant)
C3-IFS28	28	25	2020 - 2024	2020 (constant)
C4-IFS	9	5	2020 - 2049	SSP3-7.0
C4-IFS-hist	9	5	1990 - 2019	historical
C3-ICON	5	5	2020 - 2024	2020 (constant)
C4-ICON	10	5	2020 - 2049	SSP3-7.0

1.2.1 nextGEMS simulations

IFS

The Integrating Forecasting System (IFS) simulations in cycles 3 and 4 are based on version 48r1 (ECMWF, 2023), coupled to either the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean v3.4 (NEMOv3.4) or the Finite VolumE Sea ice-Ocean Model v2.5 (FESOM2.5; Rackow et al., 2023) ocean models (see Rackow et al. (2025) for more detailed descriptions). Surface processes are represented by land surface model ECLand (Boussetta et al., 2021) and the ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2018) radiation scheme is used for radiative fluxes and heating rates. Radiative transfer computations are performed on a coarsened grid and interpolated to model resolution to reduce computational costs (ECMWF, 2023). To account for subgrid cloud variability, IFS uses the Monte Carlo Independent Column Approximation (Pincus et al., 2003; Hogan and Bozzo, 2018) with a prognostic variable for cloud fraction.

In cycle 3, three 5-year simulations, starting at 20 January 2020 and with constant 2020 greenhouse gas forcing, were performed at horizontal resolutions corresponding to about 4.4 km (C3-IFS4.4), 9 km (C3-IFS9) and 28 km (C3-IFS28) in the atmosphere. In the cycle 4, two 30-year simulations with time-varying greenhouse gas, ozone, and aerosol concentrations were performed, with a horizontal resolution of about 9 km in the atmosphere: a historical run (C4-IFS-hist) starting at 1 January 1990 and a run (C4-IFS) starting 20 January 2020 that follows the SSP3-7.0 scenario (O'Neill et al., 2016). For aerosols, the time-varying climatology of Stockdale et al. (2024) was used. Except for C3-IFS9, all simulations are performed with the FESOM2.5 ocean model. Rather than switching the deep convection scheme off, the cloud base mass flux in the deep convection parametrization has been greatly reduced in the C3-IFS4.4 (factor 5)

and the cycle 4 (factor 6) simulations.

We use cycle 3 simulation data on both the native reduced Gaussian grid as well as the conservatively interpolated data at $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ and $1.0^\circ \times 1.0^\circ$ resolution. For the cycle 4 simulations, we use the highest available HEALPix (Hierarchical Equal Area IsoLatitude Pixelation; Górski et al., 2005) zoom level to which the data has been interpolated (bilinear; not conservative): zoom level 9 (≈ 12.7 km)

ICON

The Icosahedral Non-hydrostatic (ICON) simulations are based on the ICON-Sapphire model, described in detail by Hohenegger et al. (2023), with later modifications as described by (Segura et al., 2025). ICON-Sapphire (hereafter referred to as simply "ICON") is designed specifically for (sub)km-scale simulations and, compared to IFS, contains fewer parametrizations of physical processes. For example, ICON does not use parametrizations for convection or sub-grid cloud cover, the latter meaning that cloud cover is either 0 or 1. Radiative fluxes are computed using the Radiative Transfer for Energetics + RRTM for General circulation model applications-Parallel (RTE+RRTMGP; Pincus et al., 2019).

In cycle 3, one 5-year simulations (C3-ICON) with a horizontal resolution of 5 km was performed, starting at 20 January 2020, with constant 2020 greenhouse gases and the aerosol climatology of (Kinne, 2019). C3-ICON runs until 22 July 2025, but only data up to 31 December 2024 are used for consistency with IFS. In cycle 4, a 30-year simulation (C4-ICON) with 10 km resolution was performed. The simulation started 1 January 2020 and followed the SSP3-7.0 scenario, with the aerosol climatologies of Stevens et al. (2017) and Stenchikov et al. (1998). Unless stated otherwise, we use the highest resolution HEALPix zoom level to which the data has been interpolated (nearest neighbors; not conservative): zoom level 10 (≈ 6.4 km) in cycle 3 and zoom level 9 (≈ 12.7 km) in cycle 4. A constant inhomogeneity factor of 0.4 was used in the cycle 3 simulation to reduce the optical depth of liquid clouds. In cycle 4, the inhomogeneity factor varied between 0.4 and 0.8 depending on the stability of the lower troposphere (Segura et al., 2025).

1.2.2 Reference data for validation

We first use the range of reference estimates compiled by Wild (2020) to assess the accuracy of the global and annual mean surface irradiance of the simulation. For solar irradiance, these reference estimates are 187.1 W m^{-2} (Kato et al., 2018), 186 W m^{-2} (L'Ecuyer et al., 2015) and 184.7 W m^{-2} (Wild et al., 2015), averaging to 185.9 W m^{-2} . The estimates are based on the periods 2005 – 2015, 2000 – 2009 and 2000 – 2005, respectively. For thermal irradiance, based on the same periods, the reference estimates are 344.7 W m^{-2} (Kato et al., 2018), 341 W m^{-2} (L'Ecuyer et al., 2015) and 341.5 W m^{-2} (Wild et al., 2015), averaging to 342.9 W m^{-2} .

Furthermore, we use surface irradiances from the ERA5 reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2020) as well as from surface observations to assess the realism of the simulations. The ERA5 reanalysis has global coverage and a horizontal resolution of about 31 km, and is used to the

Table 4: Overview of measurement stations used for the validation of the simulations: station name, latitude (Lat), longitude (Lon), elevation (Elev), time period of used measurements, and data source. Except for Greenland AWS6, all stations are part of the BSRN network Beck et al. (2023).

Station name	Lat	Lon	Elev	Period	Reference
Cabauw	51.97°N	4.93°E	0 m	2005 - 2023	Knap (2022)
Lindenberg	52.21°N	14.12°E	125 m	1995 - 2021	Wacker and Behrens (2022)
Payerne	46.81°N	6.94°E	491 m	1993 - 2022	Vuilleumier and Heimo (2022)
Cener	42.82°N	1.60°W	471 m	2009 - 2021	Olano (2021)
Sonnblick	47.05°N	12.96°E	3109 m	2013 - 2023	Olefs (2022)
Izaña	28.31°N	16.50°E	2373 m	2009 - 2024	Torres et al. (2024)
Tamanrasset	22.79°N	5.53°E	1385 m	2000 - 2023	Baika et al. (2024)
Gobabeb	23.56°S	15.04°E	407 m	2012 - 2024	Vogt (2024)
Southern Great Plains	36.61°N	97.49°W	318 m	1994 - 2019	Riihimaki and Hodges (2024)
Tateno	36.06°N	140.13°E	25 m	1996 - 2024	Saito et al. (2024)
Brasilia	15.60°S	47.71°W	1023 m	2009 - 2015	Pereira (2015)
Greenland AWS6	67.08°N	49.40°W	1000 m	2003 - 2021	Smeets et al. (2022)

validate global spatial surface irradiance patterns. We use 33 years of data, from 1990 up to and including 2022. Surface observations enable a more accurate validation of the simulations, although with limited spatial coverage compared to the ERA5 reanalysis. Therefore, we use the high-quality irradiance measurements data of the Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN; Driemel et al., 2018). We select 11 BSRN stations spanning a wide range of locations and climate types (Table 4). To represent high-latitude arctic climate zones, we also use 18 years of data from an automatic weather station on the ice sheet of Greenland (AWS6; Smeets et al., 2018).

1.3 Validation of surface irradiance

In this section, we compare the climatologies of the downwelling surface solar and thermal irradiance of cycle 3 and cycle 4 simulations against the reference data outlined in section 1.2. By doing so, we address the hypothesis that moving towards storm-resolving horizontal resolutions results in a better representation of the mean surface irradiance.

1.3.1 Global climatology

Table 5: Global mean downwelling solar (F_{sw}^{\downarrow}) and thermal (F_{lw}^{\downarrow}) surface irradiances and differences thereof relative to the reference means ($F_{sw,ref}^{\downarrow} = 185.9 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and $F_{lw,ref}^{\downarrow} = 342.9 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, see section 1.2.2) in each simulation for the full simulation period, but omitting the year 2020 in the Cycle 3 simulations and in C4-IFS as these start at on the 20th of January. ERA5 results are 2001-2010 averages from Wild and Bosilovich (2024), CMIP6 results are 2000-2015 means from Wild (2020).

Name	$F_{sw}^{\downarrow} (\text{W m}^{-2})$	$\Delta F_{sw}^{\downarrow} (\text{W m}^{-2})$	$F_{lw}^{\downarrow} (\text{W m}^{-2})$	$\Delta F_{lw}^{\downarrow} (\text{W m}^{-2})$
C3-IFS4.4	184.6	-1.3	345.2	2.3
C3-IFS9	185.7	-0.2	345.0	2.1
C3-IFS28	183.8	-2.1	341.9	-1.0
C4-IFS	184.8	-1.1	350.5	7.6
C4-IFS-hist	185.3	-0.6	342.9	0.0
C3-ICON	201.0	15.1	336.8	-6.1
C4-ICON	190.4	4.5	343.6	0.7
ERA5	188.1	2.2	339.5	-3.4
CMIP6 mean	187.4	1.5	343.8	0.9

To assess the realism of the simulations, we first compare global and annual mean surface irradiances. Except for C3-ICON, which strongly overestimates the surface solar irradiance by 15 W m^{-2} , all simulations produce mean solar irradiances within about 5 W m^{-2} from the reference mean (Table 5). Most IFS simulations also have lower solar irradiance biases than ERA5 or the ensemble mean of the CMIP6 models, and the spread among the simulations is still well between the $\approx 20 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ CMIP6 model spread (Wild, 2020). Apart from C4-IFS and C3-ICON, thermal irradiances biases are within about 2.3 W m^{-2} and smaller in magnitude than the bias of ERA5. The -6.1 W m^{-2} bias of C3-ICON is consistent with the large positive solar irradiance bias, possibly reflecting insufficient aerosols or clouds in this simulation, or the constant inhomogeneity factor (0.4). Given that the thermal irradiance in C4-IFS-hist perfectly matches the reference mean, the 7.6 W m^{-2} thermal irradiance bias in C4-IFS (2021-2050) may be partially attributed to the later period and thus to increases in global mean temperature and humidity: In C4-IFS-hist, the mean thermal irradiance increases from 340.9 W m^{-2} in the first five years (1990-1994) to 346.2 W m^{-2} in the last five years (2014-2019), approximately consistent with the 2 W m^{-2} per decade thermal irradiance trend estimated by Wild (2017). In C4-IFS, the mean thermal irradiance is 346.8 W m^{-2} between 2021 and 2024, which is already 3.9 W m^{-2} higher than the reference mean, and increases to 354.9 W m^{-2} between 2045 and 2049. In C4-ICON,

Figure 1: Global maps of the downwelling surface solar (shortwave) irradiance F_{SW}^{\downarrow} in June-July-August (JJA) over land in the ERA5 reanalysis and the difference in JJA-mean F_{SW}^{\downarrow} between each simulation and ERA5. Data is remapped to $0.1^{\circ} \times 0.1^{\circ}$ with nearest-neighbor interpolation for visualization.

the increase in thermal irradiance is smaller, from 342.0 W m^{-2} in the first to 346.2 W m^{-2} in the last five years.

While global and annual mean irradiance biases are mostly within 8 W m^{-2} , differences between simulations may be significantly larger on regional and seasonal scales as illustrated for

Figure 2: As Figure 1, but for the downwelling surface thermal (longwave) irradiance F_{LW}^{\downarrow} .

boreal summer (June-July-August) in Figures 1 and 2. Nevertheless, absolute solar and thermal irradiance differences with respect to ERA5 are mostly within $25 W m^{-2}$ for most simulations, especially for the cycle 3 IFS simulations. The IFS simulations exhibit quite similar patterns in the deviations with respect to ERA5, irrespective of resolution, development cycle or simulation period, presumably reflecting persistent model biases. For example, all IFS simulations produce less solar and more thermal irradiance in West Africa and North America. The thermal irradiance differences in C4-IFS are mostly larger than in the other IFS simulations, again reflecting

the later simulation period.

The irradiance deviations in the ICON simulations are generally larger than in the IFS simulations, especially for solar irradiance. The worse performance of ICON compared to ERA5 may be partially attributed to the fact that ERA5 and the IFS version used within nextGEMS are both developed from the same IFS base model, and therefore not completely independent. At least for solar irradiance, however, their lower global and annual mean biases (Table 5) gives confidence in the realism of the IFS simulations. The consistent overestimation of the solar irradiance in C3-ICON is in line with its 15.1 W m^{-2} global annual mean bias (Table 5). The positive bias is even present in regions that already have very few clouds and low atmospheric moisture, such as the Sahara desert, and therefore likely not related to the representation of clouds in the simulation.

Considering the impact of resolution, the 4.4 km, 9 km and 28 km Cycle 3 IFS simulations have quite similar global annual and mean irradiances (Table 5). For solar irradiance, the absolute bias is highest in C3-IFS28 and lowest in C3-IFS9. For thermal irradiance, C3-IFS28 has the lowest absolute bias. However, if we account for a $2 - 4 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ thermal irradiance increase (Wild, 2017) between the time period on which the reference estimates are based (Section 1.2.2) and the simulation time (constant 2020), C3-IFS4.4 and C4-IFS9 would have the lowest absolute thermal irradiance bias. Global irradiance patterns in the cycle 3 IFS simulations are also similar (Figures 1 and 2), although C3-IFS28 produces lower solar irradiances, for example in Europe North-America. Nevertheless, the impact of horizontal resolution on surface irradiances is generally small, especially when compared to the differences between IFS and ICON. Locally, especially in regions with high strong gradients in orography or land cover, resolution effects may be larger.

1.3.2 Comparison against BSRN observations

For further validation of the simulations, we use solar and thermal irradiance measurements from 12 different stations (Figures 3 and 4). The ability of the simulations to capture the annual-mean irradiance climatology varies strongly between simulations, between stations, and between solar and thermal irradiance. The validation against station data again highlights the large solar irradiance bias of C3-ICON at many stations, which is generally reduced in Cycle 4 but still present for some locations (e.g. Southern Great Plains, Tateno, Brasilia). Interestingly, at some stations (e.g. Lindenberg, Payerne), thermal irradiance is underestimated by C4-IFS-hist and well-reproduced by C4-IFS, despite the time period of the measurements overlapping mostly with C4-IFS-hist (Table 4). This hints at compensating biases: a negative thermal irradiance bias in IFS and a positive bias due to warmer and moister atmospheres later in the simulation period. Figures 3 and 4 also confirm that we should be careful with using ERA5 as reference, as the nextGEMS simulations frequently outperform the ERA5 reanalysis.

Although the IFS simulations generally perform better than ICON, especially for solar irradiance, figures 3 and 4 show no clear advantage of higher resolution at most stations. For example, among the cycle 3 IFS runs, C3-IFS4.4 performs better for solar irradiance at Lindenberg and Gobabeb, whereas C3-IFS9 performs better at Sonnblick and Cener, and C3-IFS28 performs better at Tateno and Greenland AWS6. Similarly for thermal irradiance, the simulation with mean

irradiances closest to observations varies strongly between stations. At the mountain-peak stations Sonnblick and Izaña, however, thermal irradiance is overestimated in all simulations but generally improves with horizontal resolution, implying a benefit of better resolving orography: With increasing local surface elevation, we may expect a decrease in thermal irradiance due to lower atmospheric temperatures and humidities (Marty et al., 2002). However, as the Izaña station is located at about 2373 m and the grid cells covering the station in the 4.4 km, 9 km, and 28 km IFS simulations have altitudes 1602 m, 1695 m, and 377 m, respectively, the differences in thermal irradiance (figure 4f) are not fully consistent with the of $\approx -3 \text{ W m}^{-2}/100 \text{ m}$ reported by Marty et al. (2002).

Figure 3: Mean downwelling surface solar irradiance F_{SW}^{\downarrow} for each BSRN station. Black solid lines show the mean of the irradiance measurements, black dashed lines are one standard deviation, based on the yearly-mean irradiance, around the mean. Colors denote different simulation cycles, models, and simulation periods. Markers correspond to resolution (circle: $\approx 5 \text{ km}$, diamond: $\approx 10 \text{ km}$, square: $\approx 28 \text{ km}$), and whiskers show the standard deviation of the yearly-mean surface irradiance.

Figure 4: As Figure 3, but for downwelling surface thermal irradiance F_{LW}^{\downarrow} .

1.4 The impact of horizontal resolution

In this section, we aim to assess the contribution of better-resolved synoptic patterns, cloud systems, and landscape details, on differences in surface irradiance between storm-resolving and lower resolution simulations. We focus on the cycle 3 IFS simulations as these are three similar simulations (except for the different ocean model in C3-IFS9 and the reduced mass flux in C3-IFS4.4) performed with different horizontal resolutions.

1.4.1 Dominant weather

To assess the impact of different synoptic patterns, we use the objective weather type classification of the German Weather Service (Bissolli and Dittmann, 2001) which distinguishes 40 weather types based on the direction of advection, the cyclonic condition (“cyclonicity”) at 950 hPa and 500 hPa, and the humidity, for which we use total column water vapor. We adapt the classification of Bissolli and Dittmann (2001) by centering it approximately over Cabauw, the Netherlands. To emphasize grid points closer to Cabauw, all grid cells between 3°E and

Figure 5: Top row: days per year in June-July-August (JJA) classified as each 700 hPa advection type (a), humidity type (b), and 950 hPa cyclonic condition (“cyclonicity”) type (c) in the C3-IFS4.4, C3-IFS9 and C3-IFS28 simulations, following our adaptation of the objective weather system of Bissolli and Dittmann (2001). Errorbars indicate \pm one standard deviation of the number of days per year (a, b, c). Bottom row: daily mean downwelling surface solar irradiances F_{SW}^{\downarrow} (normalized by the cosine of the zenith angle) for each 700 hPa advection type (d), humidity type (e), and 950 hPa cyclonic condition (f) in the three simulations. Solid orange and dash green line show the median and mean, respectively.

7°E and between 50°N and 54°N have a weight of 3. The grid cells in the surrounding frame between 1°E and 9°E and between 48°N and 56°N have a weight of 2. The remaining grid cells between 1°W and 11°E and between 46°N and 58°N have a weight of 1. We use the data at $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ to compute the weather classification to reduce the impact of small scale variations in wind or geopotential height, e.g. near the Alps in the southwestern corner of our classification area. For each day, the classification is performed at 12 UTC. For determining the humidity type, we use the five-year monthly mean precipitable water averaged the three simulations to ensure we use the baseline for each simulation.

The JJA-mean solar irradiance near Cabauw is slightly lower in C3-IFS28 ($382.9 W m^{-2}$) than in C3-IFS4.4 ($394.8 W m^{-2}$) and C3-IFS9 ($395.7 W m^{-2}$). Figure 5 shows the mean occurrence in JJA of the different advection, humidity, and 950 hPa cyclonic condition classes for the Cycle 3 IFS simulations, along with the JJA-mean normalized solar surface irradiance per class. Although the day-to-day irradiance variability within classes and the variability between simulations are both relatively large, we do find some significant differences in daily-mean surface irradiance between weather types (Figure 5 d, e, and f): For example, surface irradiances are on average higher with anticyclonic flow, which generally correspond to higher surface pressures and more stable conditions around Cabauw, than with cyclonic flow. Similarly, surface irradi-

ances are higher with north-easterly advection (in C3-IFS4.4 also with south-easterly advection) than with advection from westerly directions, and higher in dry conditions than in wet conditions (except in C3-IFS4.4). Interestingly, we find that only in C3-IFS4.4, the relation between humidity and surface irradiance changes with the 950 hPa cyclonic condition (not shown): With anticyclonic flow, dry conditions are associated with higher surface irradiance, whereas with cyclonic flow, wet days have higher surface irradiance. However, whether this different response to wet and dry conditions depending on cyclonic conditions is statistically robust and to what extent it is the result of higher horizontal resolution, should be subject to further study.

Considering the distribution of dominant weather types, the three simulations largely agree on the frequency of the different classes, although there are some noticeable differences between the simulations (Figure 5a,b,c). For example, C3-IFS28 has more days with south-westerly advection and fewer days with north-westerly advection than the higher-resolution simulations, but this is likely not related to the differences in JJA-mean surface irradiances differences as both westerly advection directions result in similar mean surface irradiances (Figure 5d). Similarly, while C3-IFS4.4 has more wet and fewer dry days than the other two simulations, the surface irradiance difference between wet and dry conditions is negligible (Figure 5e). On the other hand, the changes in cyclonic condition compared to C3-IFS4.4 (more anticyclonic days in C3-IFS9, fewer in C3-IFS28) are consistent with the differences in solar irradiance compared to C3-IFS4.4 (higher in C3-IFS9, lower in C3-IFS28), as anticyclonic flow is associated with higher surface irradiances (Figure 5f). This correlation between cyclonic condition and solar irradiance suggests that differences in cyclonic conditions likely contribute to the differences in solar irradiance at Cabauw between the simulations.

However, since the relation between dominant weather patterns and solar irradiance is location- and climate-dependent, we cannot generalize these results at Cabauw. For example, we performed similar analyses for the Lindenberg and Southern Great Plains sites (Table 4) by centering the classification area on each of the two sites and recomputing the weather classification (not shown). At both locations, mean surface irradiances are also lowest in C3-IFS28, but with no clear relation between changes in dominant weather patterns and the differences in solar irradiance.

We should also note the results of the weather classification may be sensitive to its specific implementation. For example, days without clear (anti)cyclonic flow patterns or average atmospheric humidities may fall on either side of the binary wet/dry and anticyclonic/cyclonic classification depending on the size or weight distribution of the classification area. Although this uncertainty may be alleviated by introducing additional classes for average humidities or unspecified cyclonalities, we considered an evaluation thereof out of scope of this report.

1.4.2 Hourly cloud-driven irradiance variability

We compare the representation of the temporal irradiance variability between the cycle 3 simulations, ERA5, and the observations, to study the impact of better resolved cloud systems. To quantify the temporal variability at hourly to daily time scales, we estimate power spectral densities using Welch's method (Welch, 1967) to reduce noise at the highest frequencies, with 96 hour segments and 48 hour overlap. We also compute power spectral densities for ICON-C3

at zoom levels 10, 9, and 8. Each reduction in zoom level is a factor 4 coarsening by averaging blocks of (2×2) grid cells, which we consider representative of increasing the grid cell area without affecting the representation of convective processes.

Figure 6 shows the power spectral densities for three of the BSRN stations (Cabauw, Lindenberg, ARM Southern Great Plains). The power spectral densities peak at a time scale of 1d, with a strong harmonic component at 12h, reflecting the diurnal cycles of the solar zenith angle (solar irradiance) and atmospheric temperature (thermal irradiance). The power at sub-daily times (e.g. $\tau \lesssim 6$ h for solar and $\tau \lesssim 12$ h for thermal irradiance) is clearly underestimated by ERA5, as already shown by Stratum et al. (2023) for solar irradiance at Cabauw. Among the Cycle 3 IFS simulations, the power at shorter time scales ($\tau \lesssim 6$ h for solar $\tau \lesssim 12$ h for thermal irradiance) increases with horizontal resolution, generally converging to the observations, as expected. For thermal irradiance, C3-IFS4.4 even overestimates the temporal variability for time scales shorter than about 4 h. At time scales larger than about 2 days, the impact of horizontal resolution vanishes and the IFS simulations slightly underestimate the power spectral density, especially for solar irradiance, thus showing no sign of upscale improvements.

In C3-ICON (C3-ICON_z10 in Figure 6), the power spectral density of the solar irradiance is close to observations (but slightly higher than C3-IFS4.4), whereas for longwave irradiance the power is strongly overestimated at sub-daily timescales. Moreover, the increasing power spectral density with increasing zoom level for thermal irradiance in C3-ICON suggests that the ability of ICON to accurately capture hourly irradiance variability degrades with increasing horizontal resolution. The higher power spectral densities in C3-ICON may be partly explained by the "on-or-off" cloud cover in ICON, likely resulting in larger irradiance variations between clear and cloudy time steps than in IFS, which accounts for partial cloud cover.

Differences in the power spectral densities may also be partly explained by the temporal representativeness of the hourly irradiances in the simulations and observations. The irradiance observations have a 1 minute temporal resolution, but we subsequently resample the observations to 1 hour averages to ensure all spectra are computed with the same temporal resolution. The radiation time step in C3-ICON is 12 minutes (Hohenegger et al., 2023), but the highest temporal resolution model output is 30 minute averages, which we also resample to 1 hour averages before computing power spectra. In the IFS simulations, the full radiation computations are only performed every hour, although radiative fluxes are corrected for changes in solar zenith angle (solar irradiance) and surface temperature (thermal irradiance) at every model time step (ECMWF, 2023). Despite using hourly irradiance data, the radiative effects of clouds are only reevaluated once (IFS) or 5 times (ICON) per hour, presumably resulting in more power at the shortest time scales compared to true hourly averaged like used for observations. Indeed, we find that power spectral densities based on 10 min averages of the observations have more power at sub-daily time scales, and even more so if only the first 10 minute average of each hour is used (not shown). The surface temperature corrections in IFS likely smoothen the thermal irradiance timeseries, reducing the power at hourly time scales, which may contribute to the large differences in power spectral density of thermal irradiance between IFS and ICON. Especially for the thermal irradiance in ICON, more frequent radiative transfer computations may therefore improve the simulated irradiance variability at hourly time scales.

With the aim of distinguishing the impacts of smaller grid cell areas or explicitly resolved convec-

tion, we compare the C3-ICON data at decreasing zoom levels to the cycle 3 IFS simulations. At sub-daily time scales, the changes in power spectral density between the different zoom levels (C3-ICON) are similar in magnitude to the changes in power spectral density between C3-IFS4.4, C3-IFS9, and C3-IFS28. This similarity suggests that, among the Cycle 3 IFS simulations, the increase in power spectral density with horizontal resolution may be largely the result of the smaller grid cell area rather than a consequence of explicitly resolved convection.

Figure 6: Mean power spectral densities of the surface solar irradiance (a,b,c) and thermal irradiance (d,e,f) at Cabauw (a,d), Lindenberg (b,e) and the ARM Southern Great Plains site (c,f) for the cycle 3 IFS simulations, the cycle 3 ICON simulation at three zoom levels, ERA5, and observations. Zoom level 10 is the highest zoom level available for C3-ICON and corresponds to a resolution of about 6.4 km. Zoom levels 9 and 8 correspond to resolutions of about 12.7 km and 25.5 km, respectively

1.4.3 Orographic variability

In section 1.3.2, we illustrated for two stations located in mountainous terrain how horizontal resolution influences mean thermal irradiances. To study impact of horizontal resolution on surface irradiances via better resolved orography, we now analyze how irradiance deviations correlate with surface height variability. We use the $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ data for each simulation, which approximately corresponds to the resolution of C3-IFS28, to ensure results are not dependent on output resolution. The irradiance data are grouped in $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid boxes to compute for each grid box the mean absolute deviation (MAD) between simulations and the absolute mean deviations ($|MD|$), which is the absolute difference in $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ mean surface irradiance between simulations.

Figure 7: C3-IFS4.4 vs. C3-IFS9 (a, c) and C3-IFS4.4 vs. C3-IFS28 (b, d) mean absolute deviations (MAD) and absolute mean deviations (|MD|) of the $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ downwelling surface solar F_{SW}^\downarrow (a,b) and thermal F_{LW}^\downarrow (c,d) irradiance per $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid box, grouped by the standard deviation of the surface height within each $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid box to represent surface height variability. F_{SW}^\downarrow is normalized by the annual mean cosine of the solar zenith angle.

Surface height variability (σ_z) is quantified as the standard deviation of the $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ surface height per $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid box, computed from the C3-IFS4.4 data. While for C3-IFS4.4 and C3-IFS9, using the $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ surface height dampens the actual surface height variability at model resolution, we consider it a suitable approach for classifying regions on small-scale orography. However, note that even when interpolated to $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$, the topography is smoother in C3-IFS9 and C3-IFS28 than in C4-IFS4.4, presumably because of the smoothing operations applied when creating the orographic data at model resolution (ECMWF, 2023).

For both solar and thermal irradiance, MAD increases with increasing σ_z (Figure 7), indicating that better resolved orography affects mean local surface irradiances even after conservative interpolation to a coarser $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid. This influence of orography highlights that while IFS accounts for subgrid cloud cover heterogeneity, coarse-resolution simulations cannot fully capture small-scale variations in surface irradiance that are resolved at higher resolutions. For example, altitude-driven variations in air temperature and humidity, different cloud climatologies due to changing local flow patterns, or different snow covers (higher surface albedos result in higher downwelling solar irradiances due to the backscattering of surface-reflected radiation by cloud bases). Interestingly, while |MD| between C3-IFS4.4 and C3-IFS9 also generally in-

creases with σ_z , $|\text{MD}|$ between C3-IFS4.4 and C3-IFS28 does not exhibit a clear dependence on σ_z . This limited σ_z -dependence of $|\text{MD}|$ in combination with low magnitude of $|\text{MD}|$ compared to MAD suggests that the impacts of horizontal resolution via better resolved orography do not carry over to larger ($1^\circ \times 1^\circ$) spatial scales. Surface irradiance differences on these larger scales are likely more strongly driven by changes in prevailing weather or climate.

2 Deviations

For solar irradiance, we focused only on the global horizontal irradiance without considering the direct and diffuse components separately. Our reasons are twofold: first, direct and diffuse solar fluxes were only available for IFS, not for ICON, so that we could not compare direct/diffuse partitioning of the two models. Secondly, direct and diffuse fluxes can not be easily verified with observations as the definition of direct and diffuse radiation generally differs between models and measurements. However, we are confident that this deviation has little impact on the conclusions: for the coupling with the surface energy balances, and for applications such as the assessment of solar energy potentials, the global horizontal irradiance is the most relevant quantity.

3 Conclusion

In this report, we evaluated the surface irradiance climatology of the cycle 3 and cycle 4 nextGEMS simulations and investigate which pathways dominate the impact of horizontal resolution on mean surface irradiances.

Except for C3-ICON, global and annual mean surface irradiances are reproduced well by most simulations, with small biases up to 4.5 W m^{-2} for solar and 7.6 W m^{-2} for thermal irradiance. Furthermore, we should note that this 7.6 W m^{-2} bias in C4-IFS likely reflects the impact of global warming rather than model error. Despite low global mean biases in the simulations, local surface irradiance biases with respect to surface observations can be up to an order of magnitude larger.

Increasing the horizontal resolution does not provide a clear, consistent improvement of annual mean surface irradiances for the BSRN stations used here for validation. The high-resolution simulations only performed better than the coarser-resolution simulations in regards to thermal irradiance at the Sonnblick and Izaña stations. We find that orography is most important driver of changes in mean surface irradiance between resolutions, although that does not necessarily entail an improvement. In contrast to annual mean surface irradiances, the representation of sub-daily irradiance variability improves strongly with horizontal resolution in the cycle 3 IFS simulations, but this improvement does not carry over to synoptic time scales.

On the one hand, our results show that from the perspective of mean surface irradiances, km-scale resolutions are not yet the main path forward in climate modeling as improvements over well-tuned and well-parametrized coarse-resolution simulations are modest. On the other hand,

we can argue that the horizontal resolutions evaluated here are still too coarse to fully capture the potential of km-scale models. This is especially true for ICON, as traditionally parametrized processes such as deep convection may not yet be sufficiently resolved at 5 to 10 km resolution. Furthermore, ICON uses an inhomogeneity factor to compensate for the absence of cloud fractions, but only for liquid cloud optical depth and without consideration of partial cloud overlap (Hohenegger et al., 2023; Segura et al., 2025). However, the assumption of horizontal cloud homogeneity will likely hold increasingly well as resolution increases and clouds are better resolved.

Although the benefits of increasing the horizontal resolution on surface irradiances are still relatively small, the hope is that these km-scale simulations can serve as digital twins of the Earth system. For example, by providing data on solar irradiance, temperature, and wind speeds at high spatiotemporal resolution, these models can be used to estimate solar energy production and future trends thereof (Deliverable D9.5; Veerman, 2025). Km-scale climate simulations may then be able to support decision-making regarding the planning and design of solar photovoltaics infrastructure, which is discussed further in Deliverable D9.5 and in an upcoming manuscript focusing on renewable energy in Spain (Baulenas et al., 2025). In future work, we aim to study to what extent accounting for 3D radiative effects, such as horizontally displaced cloud shadows or orographic shading, results in different spatiotemporal surface irradiance patterns compared to conventional 1D radiative transfer approximations. Especially when moving towards $O(1)$ km resolutions, accounting for the horizontal exchange of radiation likely becomes increasingly important.

In the current stage, however, the uncertainty introduced by the small ensemble (1 scenario run each with IFS and ICON) in combination with the large model spread makes it challenging to assess the real value of these km-scale climate simulations. Additional multi-decadal historical simulations at multiple horizontal grid spacings (e.g. 5, 10, and 28 km) can provide a more robust understanding of the role of horizontal resolution on the global surface irradiance climatology in these models.

4 References

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